

TAX ELEMENTS AND THEIR PECULARITIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Kadirov Azamat Ashrafovich

Student of the faculty of Economics National University of
Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Email: azamatkadirov20030114@gmail.com

Abstract As the share of government spending in total national income increases, so does the burden on traditional sources of tax revenue. The original persistent taxes, property and capital taxes, lost their importance and were replaced by a growing dependence on income taxes, social security contributions and various sales taxes. The balance between these taxes varies significantly depending on the country, which makes different decisions about the appropriate balance between taxes.

This article examines the impact and necessity of tax elements on the country's budget. Moreover, there are indicators describing the tax which have been thoroughly investigated during the analysis.

Key words: finance, tax, tax elements, indicators describing tax, state budget.

Introduction

In the conditions of market relations, and especially during the transition to a market economy, the tax system is one of the most important regulators of economic relations. In the conditions of the market economy, taxes are one of the important means of the state influencing the economic processes, and they serve as the financial filling of budgets at various levels for the implementation of the vital support of the state. Tax payers' understanding of the objective need to pay taxes, the success of their collection is largely determined by the level of society's tax culture, which cannot be formed without an appropriate educational process for the younger generation. Through the educational system, the mass media, the tax among Uzbek is not only a forced seizure of property, but a fixed payment for public goods

consumed by each citizen, redistributing the state's output from the rich to the poor. It is possible and necessary to develop an understanding of the method of distribution in particular when tax evasion, one of the most serious crimes, only strives whilst the state is building its economic, political and social systems. The basis of the revenue side of budgets at all levels is taxes. Any state widely uses tax policy as a certain regulator of the impact on negative market phenomena. Taxes are the main income of the country's budget, so this topic is always relevant and needs to be studied.

Literature analysis

According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), when developing countries try to establish effective tax systems, they face complex problems. First, the majority of workers in these countries tend to be employed in agriculture or in the unorganized small enterprise sector. Because they rarely receive regular, fixed wages, their earnings fluctuate, with many workers being paid in cash without being reflected in the books. Therefore, the income tax base is difficult to calculate. In addition, workers in these countries usually do not spend their earnings in large stores that keep accurate records of sales and inventory. As a result, modern revenue-raising tools such as income taxes and consumption taxes play a smaller role in the economies of these countries, while the possibility of governments achieving high tax levels is effectively eliminated¹.

The textbook "Finance and Taxes" Kholmirezayev A.A., Khaidarov M.T. describes the nature of taxes, the elements of taxes and their practical significance. According to them, the elements of tax are the following: tax subject, tax object, tax subject, tax source, taxation unit, tax rate, tax benefits, tax norm, tax payment terms, tax burden, methods of calculating the tax base, tax They pointed out that the

¹ IMF Vito Tanzi Howell Zee. Tax Policy for Developing Countries, 2001

methods of weighing and others². Furthermore, the author conducted scrupulous research of the history of taxation and its elements to properly reach candid conclusions and recommendations.

Results and discussion

Taxation problems have constantly attracted the attention of economists, philosophers and statesmen of different times. F. Aquinas³ (1225 or 1226 - 1274) defined taxes as authorized robbery. S. Montesquieu⁴ (1689-1755) believed that nothing requires so much wisdom and intelligence as the definition of the part taken from the subjects and left to them. And one of the founders of the theory of taxation, A. Smith⁵ (1723 - 1790), said that taxes are not a sign of slavery, but freedom for those who pay them.

Taxes in general seem to be unpopular, while the importance of the tax system is obvious to everyone. If popular opposition is to be avoided, any acceptable system must be supported by them. An unfair tax system has caused a lot of chaos in the past. Over the years, theorists have devoted most of their ideas to determining what the basic principles of the tax system should be.

Modern tax philosophy or theory is generally considered to have started with classical economists, most notably Adam Smith. But advanced scientists such as Thomas Hobbes⁶ (1588-1639), the founder of modern political philosophy, economist and philosopher William Petty⁷ (1623-87) also made a great contribution.

² Kholmirezayev A.A, Khaidarov M.T. "Finance and Taxes" textbook. UzMU. Tashkent-2019. Page 146.

³ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Thomas Aquinas, December 2022
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/aquinas/>

⁴ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Baron de Montesquieu, Charles-Louis de Secondat
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/montesquieu/>

⁵ A. Smith./An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations
https://www.ibiblio.org/ml/libri/s/SmithA_WealthNations_p.pdf

⁶ T. Hobbes The Elements of Law, Natural and Politic, 1650

⁷ Petty, William A treatise of taxes and contributions shewing the nature and measures of [brace] crown-lands, assessments, customs, poll-moneys, lotteries, benevolence, penalties, monopolies, offices, tythes, raising of coins, harth-money, excize, &c. : with several intersperst discourses and digressions concerning [brace] warres, the church, universities, rents and purchases, usury and exchange, banks and lombards, registries for conveyances, beggars, ensurance, exportation of money/wool, free-ports, coins,

Although Hobbes is best known for his economic theories, he also focused on taxation in several of his works, including his most famous work, Leviathan. His theory of taxation is considered to be somewhat complex, and it is considered that taxation should be determined not by the wealth of the people, but by the debt owed to the state for their protection and the maintenance of the rule of law, and in the next place for military service. It also supports the provision of social security to those who cannot earn enough to live on their own labor.

Petty, in his "Treasury of Taxes and Duties"⁷ (1662), tried to formulate the principles of taxes and public expenditures that could be used by the king in raising funds for the impending war with France. He established six types of public expenditure: defense, administration, church, education, infrastructure and all types of support for the vulnerable and expenditure on primary products. He supported the expenses of the elderly, the sick, orphans and the like.

During the so-called "Long Eighteenth Century" (1688-1800), Adam Smith and his followers developed today's modern tax theory. This period was important in the development of all kinds of ideas not only in Great Britain, but also in the whole world. During these years, many important events took place, the American War of Independence, the French Revolution, which arose on the basis of tax issues. Antony Ashley Cooper, third Earl of Shaftesbury, a prominent statesman, wrote to a colleague in the Netherlands (Holland) in 1706:

There is a powerful light here that spreads itself throughout the world. It is unnatural, but word and knowledge must spread faster than ever.

This period was the era of true scholars, and there were no boundaries between disciplines or professions as there are today. Therefore, the advanced scientists of that time, John Locke, David Hume, Adam Smith, Edmund Burke, Jeremy Bentham,

housing, liberty of conscience, &c. : the same being frequently applied to the present state and affairs of Ireland.

Petty, William, Sir, 1623-1687.

London: Printed for N. Brooke ..., 1662.

Thomas Paine, despite being doctors, lawyers, academics or politicians, at the same time were moral, political and wrote philosophical works. While the author cannot include all theorists in this list, it is permissible to list the great influence of Adam Smith and his followers around the world.

He also divided income into temporary and permanent types. Permanent income can be transferred from generation to generation (for example, rent). He proposed a tax on income from sources allocated above the subsistence level.

The principle of neutrality (impartiality) that undertakes the tax system itself which should have as little influence as possible on the economic activity. This is sometimes referred to as a further development of the concept of economic efficiency and effectiveness.

Corrective control principle. In contrast to neutrality, some theorists suggest that the tax system should be used to influence attitudes. This can be useful in terms of societal behavior, such as imposing high taxes on tobacco products to discourage smoking, or tax restrictions or incentives to encourage workers to work/taxpayers to save or provide for pensions.

Variability. In other words, the system should be able to be changed without too much difficulty in order to achieve changes in economic situations.

Simplicity. The system is relatively simple to operate and understand.

Fairness. The fairness of the system is determined by who is taxed.

Accountability. The number of voters against the government.

Appropriate attitude. It defines what behavior outside the boundary is generally morally unethical. This is different from the crime tax, which is considered legal.

Talking about tax elements, the literature often indicates about the taxation system. The taxation system is a narrow concept compared to the tax system, and it actually belongs to the tax system⁸.

⁸ <https://dictionary.tsue.uz/soz/>

The tax system covers all relations related to taxes, and the system of taxation includes economic and legal relations related to the collection of taxes.

Figure 1. Revenues of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan by types of taxes (billion sums) for the years 2021-2022⁹.

Figure -1 represents taxes collected mainly from legal entities amounted to 28.9 billion soums in 2021 and 30.1 billion soums in 2022, and value added tax was more than 23.3 billion soums in 2022.

So, based on the above, the author can say that the set of methods, elements and principles of tax organization established by state legislation and collected by its special agencies is called taxation system.

Tax elements, which are considered the main link of the taxation system, are the concepts expressed in taxation, which are manifested in economic and legal relations between taxpayers and tax collectors.

Tax elements consist of several concepts, and their exact limits are not defined. Tax elements: tax subject, tax object, tax subject, tax source, taxation unit, tax rate, tax benefits, tax norm, tax payment terms, tax burden, methods of calculating the tax base, taxation methods and covers such concepts. Below is a brief explanation of each of the tax elements.

⁹ <https://finlit.uz/uz/>

Tax subject - legal and natural persons with the obligation to pay taxes, or in other words, tax subject - a mutual complex of parties that make up tax relations, in which, on the one hand, taxpayers (legal and physical individuals) on the other hand, the tax service bodies charged with tax collection - the State Tax Committee, tax departments, district and city state tax inspectorates participate. Not all legal entities and individuals are tax subjects in their activities. Because here there are legal entities and individuals who are completely exempt from taxes and cannot participate in tax relations as tax subjects. However, all tax service bodies appear as tax subjects¹⁰.

Tax agent - legal entities that withhold tax from legal entities and individuals and transfer it to the state budget. In this case, legal entities deduct and transfer to the budget the tax sums that should be withheld from wages, dividends paid as a result of direct or indirect employment by legal entities, non-resident legal entities and individuals who do not operate through a permanent establishment, remains responsible for the amount of tax not withheld, under-withheld and not transferred on time, that is, from the given evidence, the author can say that every legal entity, together with being a tax subject in tax relations, is liable for tax also participates as an agent. A tax agent is mainly recognized as a fiscal agent in the literature.

The tax object is the income, turnover and property of the taxpayer that is considered a tax and serves as a basis for taxation. Tax objects include profit or income, the value of certain goods, land area, property of individuals and legal entities, the amount of use of natural resources, etc. In fact, the object of taxation characterizes taxation of the rights of tax subjects who use, own and dispose of some of the existing material and moral wealth in the society by law. Therefore, material or spiritual wealth becomes a tax object only when the property rights to it are acquired. For example, a tax is not levied on a building without an owner, because the subject of tax is not complete in relation to a building without an owner, but even

¹⁰ https://cbu.uz/uz/press_center/reviews/584534/

if it is, the property right to this building is taxed, not the building as a tax object. From this point of view, it can be said that the tax object is actually focused on property rights and income of legal entities and individuals¹¹.

The subject of taxation is not the right to taxable income, turnover, property, etc., but to them, that is, if the subject of taxation is understood as the right to a tax subject, then the subject is understood as the owned income, land plot, building, etc. A tax object or a subject of taxation, whoever has the right to own it, has the obligation to pay the tax, that is, represents the tax subject. So, the author can say that the right to own the subject of taxation creates a tax object, and in turn, who owns this object shows the tax subject or the taxpayer.

Tax source is the source of taxes paid by the taxpayer, that is, his income. Tax object and tax source should be distinguished from each other. For some types of taxes, for example, taxes on income (profit), gross income, personal income, the tax object and tax source are the same, that is, whatever the object is, it is the source itself.

There is a distinction of the subject of taxation, the object of taxation and the source of taxation, and to reveal their nature, by specific type of tax. Looking at the land tax, the subject of its taxation is the area of the land plot, whoever has the right to own it, the tax object will appear, and what is the source of this land tax if it is paid to the state budget from the account, for example, the income obtained as a result of using the land in different ways is its source. So, based on these points, the author can say that the subject of taxation does not create an obligation to pay taxes. Returning to our example, the right to the land is given by local authorities, and at the same time, the land user has the obligation to pay taxes, because he has the right to use this land plot. Therefore, whoever has the right to own the subject of tax, he participates in tax relations as a tax subject.

¹¹ <https://finlit.uz/uz/>

Tax base is the amount to which the tax rate of the tax object is applied. The calculated amount of tax depends not only on the amount of tax rates, but also on the amount of the object to which the tax rate is applied. The amount of the tax base may vary depending on the deductions allowed from the taxable object in the legislation. It is allowed to reduce the tax base in accordance with the tax benefits provided to this category of taxpayers. It should be noted here that the tax base can be larger or smaller than the tax object. For example, as the author noted above, if the tax payer is provided with tax benefits, in such conditions, the tax base may be smaller than the tax object, and if the tax object is expanded by legislation, it may be larger.

The unit of taxation is the unit of measurement of the object. For example, in income or property tax, the unit of measurement of an object is its price in soums, while in land tax, the unit of measurement is sq.m. or hectares.

The tax rate is the standard set by the state for each unit of the object. The tax rate is the most practical element among tax elements. Because by changing tax rates, the state has a significant impact on the activities of economic entities, priority can be given to certain activities, sectors, capital can be directed to necessary sectors, and encouraged.

Tax rates are expressed in two forms: fixed rates and relative (percentage) rates. The tax rate is set at a fixed rate, and the tax is set at a fixed sum for the object. For example, a fixed amount of tax is set for each hectare of land tax. The amount of tax on the income and property of legal entities and individuals is set at a relative rate or percentage.

Tax rates can be divided into proportional, progressive and regressive types depending on the degree of connection between the tax rate and the object of taxation. The essence of the proportional tax rate is that the tax rate does not change regardless of the object of taxation. For example, the tax rate on the property of legal entities and individuals operating in the tax system of our republic remains

unchanged even if the object of tax is 1000 sums or 100,000 sums, that is, the tax object change does not affect the change of the tax rate.

Conclusion

To conclude, based on the above, there are set of methods, elements and principles of tax organization established by state legislation and collected by its special agencies is called taxation system. Tax elements, which are considered the main link of the taxation system, are concepts expressed in taxation, and they are manifested in economic and legal relations between tax payers and tax collectors.

Reference

1. IMF Vito Tanzi Howell Zee. Tax Policy for Developing Countries, 2001
2. Kholmirezayev A.A, Khaidarov M.T. "Finance and Taxes" textbook. UzMU. Tashkent-2019. Page 146.
3. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Thomas Aquinas, December 2022
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/aquinas/>
4. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy Baron de Montesquieu, Charles-Louis de Secondat <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/montesquieu/>
5. A. Smith./An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations
https://www.ibiblio.org/ml/libri/s/SmithA_WealthNations_p.pdf
6. Rejapov Kh., Turgunov T., Rakhmanov B. INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OF LOCAL BUDGET MANAGEMENT AND ITS DIRECTIONS FOR APPLICATION IN THE COUNTRY // Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science. 2020. №49-2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/international-experience-of-local-budget-management-and-its-directions-for-application-in-the-country>.
7. T. Hobbes The Elements of Law, Natural and Politic, 1650
8. Petty, William A treatise of taxes and contributions shewing the nature and measures of [brace] crown-lands, assessments, customs, poll-moneys, lotteries, benevolence, penalties, monopolies, offices, tythes, raising of coins, harth-money,

excize, &c. : with several intersperst discourses and digressions concerning [brace] warres, the church, universities, rents and purchases, usury and exchange, banks and lombards, registries for conveyances, beggars, ensurance, exportation of money/wool, free-ports, coins, housing, liberty of conscience, &c. : the same being frequently applied to the present state and affairs of Ireland. Petty, William, Sir, 1623-1687. London: Printed for N. Brooke ..., 1662.

9. Davlat qarzlarini boshqarish [Matn]: o‘quv qo‘llanma / O.S.Komolov, A.Z.Abdullayev, X.X. Rejapov. – Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2023. – 306 b.

10. Abdunazarova Sh.N., Rejapov X.X. Mahalliy budjetlar barqarordaromadlarini ta’minlash yo‘nalishlari // RESEARCH AND EDUCATION ISSN: 2181-3191 VOLUME 1 // ISSUE 2 // 2022
<https://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/655/652>

11. Central bank. Budget <https://finlit.uz/uz/articles/budget/>

12. https://cbu.uz/uz/press_center/reviews/584534/

13. <https://finlit.uz/uz/>